

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-15-IC-1% 05 RAC	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	10	Acq. Method Set:	1%210400 05
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	LRM 4 15
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	60.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	3/8/2023 9:38:14 PM CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 10:27:39 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	9.808	94405	1.50	3207
2	11.581	3031792	48.30	97374
3	13.441	3045672	48.52	95327
4	15.070	104719	1.67	2918

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-14-IC-1% 05 ASY	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	11	Acq. Method Set:	1%210400 05
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	LRM 4 14
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	21.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	3/8/2023 10:00:41 PM CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 10:28:57 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	10.255	389	0.00	-71
2	12.110	147395	1.13	4483
3	13.965	12866307	98.77	384729
4	15.486	12214	0.09	-533